

Comparison between Water-Retted and Enzyme-Treated Decorticated Banana Fibres

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Abstract:

Background

Banana is one of India's most cultivated crops, with an estimated area of 880 thousand hectares. The banana pseudo stems, which are the residue of banana cultivation (accounting for approximately 30 tonnes per acre in one crop season), are generally left in fields or taken to open dumps or burnt along the roadside, where they produce greenhouse gases. Banana fibres extracted from a pseudostem with alpha-cellulose and low lignin content are underutilized for use in different applications.

Method

The present study aimed to optimize the removal of tissues on fibres using the pectinase enzyme at various concentrations and to compare the diameter and strength of the fibres with those of water-retted fibres. The fibre diameter was determined through scanning electron microscopy. The tensile strength was evaluated using a universal tensile tester.

Result & Conclusion

The results indicated the potential of using enzyme-treated banana fibres for textile applications.

Keywords: Banana Pseudostem Fibres, Enzyme Retting, Fibre Extraction Method, Natural Fibres, Pectinase, Sustainable Fibres

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1 Introduction

Globally, scientists have been working on utilizing natural fibres for their potential applications [1, 2, 3] owing to the development of global environmental challenges, which include global warming [4] and a decrease in petroleum supplies. Cotton is the most commonly used natural fibre since it provides exceptional qualities, including being easily accessible, biodegradable, strong, renewable, lightweight, highly absorptive as well as having optimized methods and machines for processing. However, cotton production requires a large amount of water and can be chemically intensive, with pesticides [5] compared to other crops. To overcome the problem of cotton, there is increased interest in the field of textiles to develop a portfolio of natural fibres that can replace cotton. The need for eco-friendly and sustainable textiles can be met using nonconventional natural fibres such as fibres extracted from banana pseudostems since they have low density, high tensile strength, low elongation at break and high tensile modulus [6].

Banana is one of the major agricultural products in the world, with an estimated 119.83 million tonnes produced annually in 2020 [7]. It is cultivated in 130 different countries, making local banana waste widely available [4]. Within 130 countries, India is the world's largest banana producer, growing more than 31 million tons a year in 2020 [8]. The banana plant pseudostem (made with a soft core and surrounding leaf sheaths) accounts for the majority of banana waste biomass [9] and is either dumped or burned in fields, which greatly threatens the environment by releasing greenhouse gases [4]. However, banana biomass waste, which contains significant amounts of cellulose and hemicellulose, can be extracted from fibre with improved fineness and spinnability [11,

12]. This approach helps reduce the dependency on natural (cotton), synthetic, and manmade fibres, which require energy, fertilizer, and chemicals [9] in the manufacturing process. Further development and production of banana fibre in the textile industry will serve as an energetic impetus, providing employment and income for farmers [12], innovators, entrepreneurs, and small-scale industries.

The fibre from the banana plant can be extracted through retting, although its characteristics vary depending on the preparation, separation, processing, and extraction process. Banana fibres are traditionally extracted manually, which is a laborious technique, and the quality of the fibres obtained is based on the laborer's skills [14, 15]. Currently, different extraction techniques commonly used include water retting, dew retting, mechanical extraction, and enzymatic treatment.

Water retting involves immersing the pseudostem in water wherein the water penetrates the plant stems and causes the internal cells to swell, resulting in busting of the outer layer [15]. The fibres were extracted manually, washed, and sundried. This process is widely practiced since it has the advantages of good-quality uniform fibres. However, water retting is considered to be an expensive and time-consuming process, causing environmental pollution [16]. The mechanical decorticating technique involves cutting banana stems, crushing them between two drum rollers, and post cleaning and filtering contaminants to produce environmentally friendly and economical fibres. Natural binding material or lignin cannot be removed by this method [17], resulting in incomplete detachment of fibres [4]. The disadvantages of the mechanical extraction method (limitation of removing naturally binding material from fibre bundles) [1, 4 & 19] and water retting (dependency on clean water) can be met with an alternative sustainable method such as enzyme treatment.

A comparative study on mechanically extracted banana fibres with banana fibres subjected to biological extraction using commercial protease and pectinase reported that the biologically extracted fibres exhibited favourable tensile strength and elongation properties [19]. Similarly, another research compared three extraction methods for banana fibres: chemical extraction using sodium hydroxide (NaOH), mechanical extraction, and biological extraction using pectinase. It has been reported that the diameter of fibres extracted using chemicals resulted in a 30% reduction compared to biological and mechanical extraction, whereas biologically extracted fibres have a 40% increase in fibre strength compared to other two fibre extraction methods [20]. The pectinase derived from *Aspergillus Niger* and *Aspergillus fumigatus* was used to develop an environmentally friendly process for degumming and extracting banana fibres [21]. From similar studies, it was evident that the use of pectinase helps in the degumming of fibres by removing interlamellar pectin, leading to enhanced fibre yield compared to alternative methods. Furthermore, this approach contributes to reduced environmental impact, lower water consumption, and a more efficient extraction process [4, 23].

Investigating green manufacturing techniques for extracting fibres from agricultural wastes while ensuring sustainability holds paramount importance in mitigating environmental issues. The present study focused on the utilization and enhancement of fibre extraction efficiency from agricultural waste, specifically from banana pseudostems, through enzymatic treatment using varying concentrations of pectinase enzymes for degumming. The extracted fibres are subsequently subjected to testing and comparison against water-retted fibres to assess their physical and morphological characteristics.

2 Materials and Methods

A mixed study of quantitative, qualitative, and experimental research methods was used in this research to determine the optimal enzyme concentration for the treatment of decorticated banana fibres, thereby ensuring the production of high-quality fibres. Furthermore, the present investigation encompasses the analysis of various properties and characteristics associated with the extracted banana fibres that commenced in March 2022, at Department of Design, MSAP, Manipal. Mechanical decortication machine is used to decorticate fibres from the pseudostem after which the fibres are subjected to treatment with selected enzyme concentrations. For the water-retting process, banana pseudostems are submerged in stagnant water tank until the fibres naturally separate from the pseudostem. A diagrammatic representation of the study is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Flow Chart of the Extraction Process

2.1 Materials

The banana plants were collected from the farmer’s field in Coastal Karnataka after fruit harvest in month of April 2022. The taping top and the broad bottom ends of the pseudostems are cut, and the pseudostem is utilized for extracting the fibres. Pectinase for the enzyme treatment was obtained from Sigma Aldrich, while mechanical decortication machines were used for the extraction of banana pseudostems.

2.2 Fibre Extraction Methods

The fibre was extracted by water retting, decortication, and decortication followed by enzyme treatment at different concentrations. The nomenclature and identification of various fibre samples via the extraction method are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 - Nomenclature of various fibre samples

Sample	Nomenclature
Water Retted Fibre	WRF
Decorticated Fibre	DF
Enzyme Treated Fibre 0.5%	ETF 0.5%
Enzyme Treated Fibre 0.7%	ETF 0.7%
Enzyme Treated Fibre 1%	ETF 1%

2.2.1 Water Retting

During water retting, the cut strip of the banana pseudostem was submerged in the water at 28⁰ to 32⁰ C for 10 days. After 10 days, the decayed stems were removed, cleaned thoroughly with running water and combed with a fine comb to clean the fibres from adhering to the remaining tissues [17].

2.2.2 Mechanical Extraction

The mechanical fibre extraction techniques using a decortication machine help to maintain the length of the fibre, reduce mechanical damage, save water and time [23]. The mechanical fibre extraction was performed by cutting the banana pseudostem in half, and the sheaths were detached layer by layer using a knife. Freshly cut banana pseudostem strips are fed between a scraping and squeezing roller of a decorticating machine that separates the pulp from the sheath [17, 21] and leaves only the fibres. The decorticated fibre was air-dried for 24 hours.

2.2.3 Standardization of Banana Pseudostem Decorticated Fibres for Enzyme Treatment

Banana fibres are treated with pectinase (Sigma–Aldrich) for degumming, it removes pectins, fats, and waxes from the surface and softens the fibre. The freshly decorticated banana pseudo stem fibres were immersed in a 1:20 MLR (material to liquor ratio) enzyme bath at different concentrations [24]. The temperature and pH were maintained according to technical information. After the enzyme treatment, the fibre samples were thoroughly rinsed to prevent additional reactions. The parameters used for different enzyme concentrations are depicted in Table 2.

Table 2 - Optimization of parameters for the degumming of banana pseudostem fibres using the enzyme pectinase

Parameters	Values		
	Pectinase Concentration (% owf)	0.5%	0.7%
Time (Min)	15		
MLR	1:20		
Temperature(°C)	100		
pH	5.5		

2.3 Fibre Yield Obtained from the Different Methods

The amount of fibre obtained from each of the different methods was determined using the following formula:
 $\text{Yield\%} = [\text{OD weight of the extracted fibre} / \text{OD weight of the plant part used for extraction}] \times 100$ [25].

2.4 Weight Loss of the Extracted Banana Fibres

The reduction in the weight loss of the banana fibres is the decrease in the overall mass due to the loss of hemicellulose, fluid and lignin content, etc. during fibre extraction methods such as water retting and mechanical decortication followed by enzyme treatment. The weight loss of the extracted fibres was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Weight loss\%} = [(IW - AW) / IW] \times 100$$
 [26]

where IW is the mass before treatment (gm) and AW is the mass after treatment (gm).

2.5 Evaluation of the Physical Properties of Banana Fibres

2.5.1 Determination of Tensile Strength

Using a universal tensile tester machine and a 27-centimeter test sample length, the maximum force necessary to break the fibres was measured and the ultimate tensile strength was calculated using the following formula:

$$\sigma = F / A$$
 [27]

where F is the load and A is the cross-sectional area.

2.5.2 Determination of Fibre Length

The direct method was used to measure the length of single banana fibre. Both ends of the single fibre are grasped by tweezers and the fibre is held without much tension alongside the steel ruler. After 50 measurements were taken, the average was calculated [28].

2.5.3 Determination of Fibre Diameter

Fibre samples were tested with an average diameter of 10 readings using an SEM analysis with a magnification factor of 100 to 400X [20].

2.5.4 Determination of the Fibre Color and Texture

The color and texture of the raw fibres are analysed by the naked eye, while hand evaluation is subjective. A panel of 10 members was asked to see, touch, and feel [24] treated samples that were anonymously labelled as per Table 1.

2.5.5 Morphological analysis

The morphological structure of the banana fibre samples was examined using an SEM analysis. The sample was set up on a pin stub and placed on a holder to keep inside the SEM chamber. The samples are observed under a magnification of 100 to 400X [20], and the longitudinal view of the fibres is analysed.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Fibre Yield and Weight Loss of Extracted Fibres

A comparison of the extracted fibres shows that the weight loss of the water-retted fibres (WRF) is greater than that of the decorticated fibres (DF). The decorticated fibres treated with pectinase showed considerable weight loss, an increase in enzyme concentration resulted in a decrease in weight loss as shown in Table 3.

Table 3 - Fibre Yield and Weight Loss of Extracted Banana Fibres

Sample	Weight of pseudostem used for extraction	Weight of Extracted pseudostem fibres	Yield %	Weight of the pseudostem/fibres before treatment	Weight of the pseudostem/fibres after treatment	Weight loss%
WRF	50 gm	23.4 gm	46.8%	50 gm	23.4 gm	53.2%
DF	50 gm	36.3 gm	72.6%	50 gm	36.3 gm	27.4%
ETF 0.5%	-	-	-	50 gm	38.6 gm	22.8%
ETF 0.7%	-	-	-	50 gm	42.4 gm	15.2%
ETF 1%	-	-	-	50 gm	43.8 gm	12.4%

3.2 Physical Properties of Banana Fibres

The physical properties of the banana fibres (tensile strength, color, texture, length, diameter, and morphological structure) are described below.

3.2.1 Tensile Strength of the Banana Fibres

The average bundle strength of the extracted banana fibre is shown in Table 4.

Table 4 - Tensile Strength of Banana Fibre Samples

Samples	Ultimate Tensile Strength (UTS)	Maximum Force
WRF	11.53 N/mm ²	12.89 N
DF	17.79 N/mm ²	73 N
ETF 0.5%	4.76 N/mm ²	6.23 N
ETF 0.7%	3.11 N/mm ²	4.08 N
ETF 1%	2.47 N/mm ²	3.24 N

The data presented in Table 4 show that DF has 17.79 N/mm² as a UTS and 73 N as the maximum force, followed by WRF, ETF 0.5%, ETF 0.7%, and ETF 0.1%. The tensile strength of the fibres decreased with increasing enzyme concentration.

3.2.2 Fibre Diameter and Length

The average diameter and length of the banana fibres are shown in Table 5.

Table 5 - Length and Diameter of the Fibre Samples

Samples	Length of the stem before extraction/treatment	Length of the fibres after extraction/treatment	Diameter
WRF	100 cm	95-98 cm	204 μ
DF	100 cm	70-90 cm	503 μ
ETF0.5%	100 cm	70-90 cm	502 μ
ETF0.7%	100 cm	70-90 cm	573 μ
ETF 1%	100 cm	70-90 cm	406 μ

The data presented in Table 5 show that after treatment, compared with the other fibre samples, the WRF had 95 cm to 98 cm long fibres. The ETF 0.7% had the greatest diameter of 573 μ , followed by DF, ETF 0.5%, ETF 1%, and WRF. WRF had the lowest diameter of 204 μ compared to the other samples.

3.2.3 Fibre Color and Texture

Digital photographs of the fibres extracted using three methods, such as water retting, mechanical extraction, and enzyme treatments are depicted in Figure 2. WRF is smooth, clean, and white in color, while DF is stiff and light yellow in color.

The banana fibres are evaluated for hand properties by a panel of 10 staff members of the Department of Design. The panel has rated WRF being the best for hand properties followed by ETF 0.5%, ETF 0.7%, ETF 1%, and DF. The stiffness of the decorticated enzyme-treated fibres increased with increasing enzyme concentration. The ETF 0.5% treated fibres were softer, cleaner, and brighter than the ETF 0.7% and ETF 1% treated fibres. The ETF 0.5% is brighter than ETF 0.7% fibre, which is found to be a light brown colour, and ETF 1% fibre is yellowish in color.

A) WRF, B) DF, C) ETF 0.5%, D) ETF 0.7%, E) ETF 1%
Figure 2 - Digital Photographs of Banana Pseudostem Fibres

3.2.4 The Morphological Properties of Banana Fibres

The longitudinal structure of the banana pseudostem fibres was examined using SEM micrographs at magnifications ranging from 100X to 400X. The SEM images revealed the presence of partially separated binder materials on the surface of WRF, DF, ETF 0.5%, ETF 0.7% and ETF 1% extracted fibres. Fig. 3A reveals that the binder material was removed and shows that the fibres were cleaner, while Fig. 3C, 3D, 3E show cleaner and more rough fibres compared to those of the Fig.3A. Among the enzyme-treated fibres, ERF 0.5% exhibited good results, followed by ERF0.7% and ERF1%. Fig. 3B displays the SEM image of DF, which shows a cloudy, scaly fibre surface due to the presence of the binder (waxy substance, lignin, hemicellulose, and cellulose). However, the presence of binder content occupying the spaces in the fibre can contribute to the strength and greater diameter [20]. The presence of adhering tissue and a rough surface was observed in the DF sample, while it was not prominent in the fibres extracted using other methods.

A) WRF, B) DF, C) ETF 0.5%, D) ETF 0.7%, E) ETF 1%
Figure 3 - SEM image of banana pseudostem fibre samples

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study provides key insights into banana pseudostem fibre behaviour, particularly under enzyme treatment compared to water retting. This research demonstrated that enzymatic processing significantly enhances the physical and subjective qualities of decorticated fibres, surpassing the effectiveness of water retting. Notably, the study identified 0.5% pectinase as the optimal concentration for minimizing tissue content, highlighting the potential advantages of enzyme-retted applications. Scanning electron microscopy analysis further validated the efficacy of enzyme treatment by revealing damaged fibres in mechanically extracted samples, emphasizing the

removal of binder materials in both water-retted and enzyme-retted fibres. These findings underscore the promising prospects of enzyme treatment for obtaining high-quality fibres, with implications for textile and apparel production.

The present study advocates for continued exploration and focused research in the realm of banana fibre extraction to harness its full potential for sustainable and superior-quality textiles.

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